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Research Article

EFFICACY OF PERCUTANEOUS TENDON NEEDLING FOR LATERAL EPICONDYLITIS

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Abstract:

Lateral epicondylitis (LE) is the most common cause of elbow and forearm pain in adults. The techniques used in dry needling varied across the primary studies and it was often combined with other treatment interventions. To address LE different types of treatments have been used. Corticosteroid (CS) injections and dry needling (DN) are utilized options in the treatment.

Study Settings: Department of Surgery

Study Design: Randomized controlled trial

Duration Of Study: Six (6) months (Nov, 2018 to April, 2019)

Objective: Efficacy of DN versus CS injection treatment in management of LE in terms of improvement of VAS and PRTEE score.

Material And Methods: All LE patients whose pain was not relieved by 3 weeks of first-line treatment were included in randomized manner, using computer generated number into DN (dry needling) or CS (corticosteroid) groups. The minimum follow-up duration was 6 months. We recorded "Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation" (PRTEE) scores before treatment, and after 3 weeks and 6 months of treatment.

Results: VAS scoring and PRTEE score in both the groups at baseline and after 3 weeks of treatment were compared in 65 patients each. Efficacy of DN was 41% and that of CS group was 52.3% (p=0.21).

Conclusion: Both DN and CS treatment of LE are almost equally effective. Patients can choose the treatment modality after discussion with the treatment physician. Further studies should be done to compare any adverse effects and improvement in the functional outcome after treatment. Keywords: Dry needling, Epicondylitis, Steroids, Tennis elbow,

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INTRODUCTION:

Lateral epicondylitis, or tennis elbow, is the most common cause of elbow and forearm pain in adults, with an annual incidence of 1% to 3% in the general population. Lateral epicondylitis is thought to be related to overuse of the extensor carpi radialisbrevis muscle, producing pain in the lateral elbow and forearm region.¹ Although the role of inflammation in the pathophysiology of this condition is questionable, lateral epicondylitis is postulated to involve degenerative changes in the epicondylar entheses of the extensor carpi radialisbrevis and perhaps also the supporting collateral ligamentous complex and joint capsule². Uncertainty regarding the pathologic basis of lateral epicondylitis underlies, in part, the lack of consensus on optimal management. The natural history of lateral epicondylitis typically includes resolution in 6 to 24 months, and symptoms remit in approximately 80% of patients within 1 year.³

Dry needling and acupuncture as alternative and less invasive procedures, trigger points. Dry needling has been shown to alter the biochemical environment and reduce spontaneous electrical activity within the skeletal muscle.⁴ Although the use of dry needling appears to be increasing, it is not clear whether there is good evidence that this procedure is clinically effective.⁵

The techniques used in dry needling varied across the primary studies and it was often combined with other treatment interventions (such as exercise therapy or injections). Comparators to dry needling included: exercise or stretching, physiotherapy, compression, injections (of saline, anesthetics (such as lidocaine), corticosteroids, botulinum toxin, platelet-rich plasma (PRP) or other types of autologous blood products), various types of acupuncture, extracorporeal shockwave therapy (ESWT), transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), percutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (PENS), laser, drug therapies, sham or superficial needling, placebo, or "usual care".⁶ Low to moderate evidence suggests a positive effect of dry needling for pain, pain-related disability, pressure pain sensitivity and strength at short-term in patients with lateral epicondylalgia of musculoskeletal origin.⁷

In a study, after treatment DN-treated patients showed better improvement in the PRTEE score than CS-treated patients ($p < 0.01$). Both treatments were effective (both $p < 0.01$). From assessments at 3 weeks and 6 months post-treatment, PRTEE scores decreased over time.⁸

Study showed that results showed that, according to the visual analog scores, 24 of the 49 patients (49%) in the corticosteroid group were successful.⁹ Another study reported that the improvement was 34 % in the dry needling group when managing LE cases.¹⁰

The rationale of this study is that Lateral epicondylitis (LE) is a common disease especially at middle age. To address LE different types of treatments have been used. Corticosteroid (CS) injections and dry needling (DN) are utilized options in the treatment. However, the question of which one is better has not been entirely discussed in the literature. As no local data is available, I have designed this study to determine the efficacy of DN versus CS injection treatment in management of LE in terms of improvement of VAS and PRTEE score.

OBJECTIVE:

To compare the efficacy of DN versus CS injection treatment in management of LE in terms of improvement of VAS and PRTEE score.

HYPOTHESIS:

There is difference in the efficacy of DN versus CS injection treatment in management of LE in terms of improvement of VAS and PRTEE score.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS:**A. DRY NEEDLING:**

Dry needling' refers to the insertion of thin monofilament needles, without the use of injectate to relieve pain.

B. LE – Lateral Epicondylitis:

Any patient with pain on the lateral side of the elbow and at the lateral epicondyle on palpation and during resisted dorsiflexion of the wrist will be labeled as having LE.

C. Efficacy in terms of improvement in VAS and PRTEE score:

Successful treatment will be defined as more than a 25% reduction in visual analog score or Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation - PRTEE score.

VAS- Visual analog score: scale of 0 to 10 with no pain = 0 score and worst possible pain = 10

Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation - PRTEE score: (Annexure I)

MATERIALS & METHODS:**STUDY SETTINGS:**

Department of orthopedic

STUDY DESIGN:

Randomized controlled trial

DURATION OF STUDY:

Six (6) months after proper approval of synopsis

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Non-probability consecutive sampling

Sample Size:

Sample size was calculated using WHO sample size calculator

Expected efficacy of DN = P1 = 34%¹⁰ versus that of CS = P2 = 49%⁹

Power of test = 80% level of significance = 5%

Sample size =130 (65 in each group)

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

All LE patients whose pain was not relieved by 3 weeks of first-line treatment were included in randomized manner, using computer generated number into DN (dry needling) or CS (corticosteroid) groups. The minimum follow-up duration was 6 months. We recorded "Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation" (PRTEE) scores before treatment, and after 3 weeks and 6 months of treatment.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Age <18 years
2. Treatment with corticosteroid injection within 3 months
3. Known case of inflammatory diseases
4. Known case of diseases causing chronic pain

DATA COLLECTION:

After the approval to carry out this study from the Ethical Review Committee, neonates presenting in the hospital meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be included in the study after informed consent from the parents.

TABLE No. 1**AGE DISTRIBUTION (n=130)**

Age(in years)	dry needling (n=65)		Corticosteroid (n=65)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
19-40	41	63.08	46	70.77
41-60	24	36.92	19	29.23
Total	65	100	65	100
Mean±SD	38.44±6.97		37.67±5.81	

In the CS group, injection 1 mL triamcinolon, 40 mg/mL + 2 mL lidocaine, 10 mg/mL was delivered through 1 site. After treatment, the patients were asked to use the arm minimally for 3 days and then gradually return to normal use. The minimum follow-up duration was 3 weeks. Outcome was recorded in terms of "Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation" (PRTEE) scores before treatment, and after 3 weeks of treatment. The minimum follow-up duration was 6 months. We recorded "Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation" (PRTEE) scores before treatment, and after 3 weeks.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. Mean and standard deviation was calculated for quantitative / continuous variables and percentage was calculated for categorical variables like gender, and efficacy. The results were presented in the form of tables. Mean VAS and PRTEE score of each group was compared using paired sample t- test. P-value of < 0.05 will be considered significant. Efficacy will be compared using chi square test. P-value of < 0.05 will be considered significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 130(65 in each group) who fulfilled the selection criteria were enrolled to compare the efficacy of DN versus CS injection treatment in management of LE in terms of improvement of VAS and PRTEE score.

The detailed analysis of results is as below: Table no 1 shows the age distribution along with gender distribution of patients in both groups. It also shows the VAS scoring and PRTEE score in both the groups at baseline and after 3 weeks of treatment.

TABLE No. 2
GENDER DISTRIBUTION (n=130)

Gender	dry needling (n=65)		Corticosteroid (n=65)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Male	40	61.54	42	64.62
Female	25	38.46	23	35.38
Total	65	100	65	100

TABLE No. 3

COMPARISON OF EFFICACY IN BOTH GROUPS(n=130)

Efficacy	dry needling (n=65)		Corticosteroid (n=65)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Yes	27	41.54	34	52.31
No	38	58.46	31	47.67
Total	65	100	65	100

P value=0.21

DISCUSSION:

Lateral epicondylitis, commonly called tennis elbow, is one of the common disorders of the elbow joint. It is characterized by micro tears in extensor carpi radialis brevis muscle leading to pain on the outer side of the joint.¹¹ Multiple management strategies of non-surgical nature are now available; these include treatments like physiotherapy; elbow-strap; extracorporeal-shock waves therapy; superficial nitrate application; corticosteroid therapy, botulinum therapy, PRP therapy (platelet-rich plasma) and dry needling technique.^{12,13}

Dry needling (DN) technique is not inferior to corticosteroid therapy in reducing pain due to infection and in improvement of function in patients with bony pains in various conditions like Greater Trochanteric Pain Syndrome, epicondylitis, subacromial pain syndrome, etc. Some studies concluded that DN is neither superior nor inferior to cortisone injection, while some studies suggested that DN is better than cortisone injection.^{14,15} It is safe as reported by many studies but still few complications can occur like pain with needling, local hematoma, and rarely it can trigger syncope. Overall this technique is categorized as low-risk, least invasive and relatively cheap, with ease in the performance.¹⁶

Multiple controlled trials have been done in the world and studies have been published comparing effectiveness and safety of different methods in the treatment of LE. Still ideal treatment of LE varies between populations. Attitude of the patients towards the treatment of LE also matters, many a times patients take LE as a self-limiting condition. Every treatment modality has its pros- and cons. DN often requires sessions and patients are called multiple

times after appointments. Needling can be more time taking compared to just a single injection of steroid for the treatment of LE.¹⁷ Compared to other treatment modalities, in terms of effectiveness, DN and CS are better but which of them can be more cost effective and efficient at the same time is still a matter of debate specially for our population.

Uygun E, et al. reported Seven patients were excluded for various reasons; thus, 101 patients were finally evaluated. The mean patient ages were 47.5 ± 7.3 years (range, 29-64) in group I and 48.1 ± 10.3 years (range, 32-69) in group II ($P = .438$). The mean symptom duration prior to treatment was 8.4 ± 3.2 months (range, 3-12) in group I and 8.3 ± 2.5 months (range, 3-14) in group II. Before treatment, the groups were similar in terms of age, symptom duration, and PRTEE score, but after treatment, DN-treated patients showed better improvement in the PRTEE score than CS-treated patients ($P < .01$). Both treatments were effective (both $P < .01$). baseline score in DN group: 60.9 ± 11.8 dropped to 15.6 ± 7.7 after 3 weeks; and in the CS group this was 58.6 ± 5.1 dropped to 36 ± 14.7 . From assessments at 3 weeks and 6 months post-treatment, PRTEE scores decreased over time. Both treatments were effective ($P < 0.01$ for DN group and 0.03 p value for CS group). Four CS-treated patients (7.6%) developed skin atrophy and whitening. One DN-treated patient (2.04%) could not tolerate the pain of the intervention and withdrew from treatment.

In a study, after treatment DN-treated patients showed better improvement in the PRTEE score than CS-treated patients ($p < 0.01$). Both treatments were effective (both $p < 0.01$). From assessments at 3

weeks and 6 months post-treatment, PRTEE scores decreased over time.¹⁸

Results of another study showed that, according to the visual analog scores (VAS), 24 of the 49 patients (49%) in the corticosteroid group were successfully treated.¹⁹ Another study reported that the improvement was 34 % in the dry needling group when managing LE cases.²⁰

Barnes DE, et al. also conducted a similar type of randomized controlled trial, showing an improvement of the VAS pain score from 6.4 at baseline to 0.7 at 12 months post-treatment in the dry needling group.²¹

CONCLUSION:

Both DN and CS treatment of LE are almost equally effective. Patients can choose the treatment modality after discussion with the treatment physician. Further studies should be done to compare any adverse effects and improvement in the functional outcome after treatment.

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